

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF BIOACTIVE LIPBALM INCORPORATING JACKFRUIT (*ARTOCARPUS HETEROPHYLLUS*) SEED EXTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate an herbal lip balm containing **jackfruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*)** seed extract as a natural bioactive ingredient. Jackfruit seeds are rich in phytochemicals, carbohydrates, proteins and antioxidant compounds that may offer beneficial cosmetic properties. Fresh jackfruit seeds were collected, dried, powdered, and subjected to ethanolic Soxhlet extraction method to obtain the bioactive extract. In this study, herbal lip balm formulation was prepared using natural excipients including beeswax, cocoa butter, coconut oil, almond oil, and vitamin E with varying concentration of jackfruit seed extract. The prepared formulation was evaluated for physiochemical parameters such as appearance, pH, melting point, spread ability, stability. The presence of jackfruit seed extract showed potential antioxidant properties, supporting its possible application in herbal lip care

products. The study indicates that jack fruit seed extract can be explored as a promising natural ingredient for innovative cosmetic formulation.

KEYWORDS: Jackfruit seed extract, Lip balm, Moisturizing, Herbal cosmetics.

INTRODUCTION

Lip balm is a semisolid preparation applied to the lips to moisture, protect, and prevent dryness, cracking, and chapping of the lips. The formulation contains waxes, oil, butter, and active ingredients which help to maintain lips hydration and improve lip health and protect

from environmental factors like sunlight, cold weather, wind, and dehydration. It forms a protective barrier on the lip surface.

MECHANISM OF ACTION OF LIPBALM

Lip balm acts mainly through occlusion, moisturization, and protection. It forms a protective layer over the lips, reducing trans epidermal water loss and help to improve hydration. Waxes such as beeswax function as occlusive agents that prevent moisture loss. While oils and emollients improve softness, lubrication, and smoothness of the Lips. Jack fruit seed extract containing phenolic compounds and flavonoids, may contribute antioxidant activity and support lip protection against oxidative stress.

ANATOMY OF LIPS

Lips are soft tissue structures present at the opening of the oral cavity and are involved in speech, mastication, and facial expression.

Anatomically lips consist of

- Outer skin layer
- Vermilion border
- Muscular layer
- Inner mucosal layer

The **vermilion border** is the region between the outer skin and the inner mucosa. Responsible for the natural red color of the lips. Richly supplied with blood vessels.

- Lips differ from normal skin because they
- Have a thin protective layer
- Do not contain sweat gland
- Show low sebaceous gland secretion

Therefore, lips are easily affected by dryness, dehydration, and chapping. The main muscle associated with lip movement is the **orbicularis Oris muscle**. The inner side of the lips contains non-keratinized epithelium and minor salivary glands that help in maintaining moisture. Blood supply is mainly through **superior and inferior labial arteries**. Because lips lose moisture easily, lip balm formulation is to provide protection, hydration, and maintenance of lip health.

JACKFRUIT

Scientific Name: *Artocarpus heterophyllus* Common name: Jackfruit Jack tree Family: Moraceae Jackfruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*) is a tropical fruit widely distributed in countries like Brazil, Thailand, Indonesia, India, and Malaysia. Its seeds are important, which is rich in nutrients such as starch, proteins, minerals and various phytochemicals.

Phenolic compounds and flavonoids - Antioxidant properties, which protect lips from oxidative stress.

Starch- texture, consistency and formulation stability.

Fatty acids- Emollient and moisturizing.

Due to these bioactive constituents, jackfruit seeds have been used in applications like food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic formulations, including topical preparations such as lip balm.

Fig. 1.1: Jackfruit.

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
Common Name	Jack Fruit
Botanical Name	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>
Family	Moraceae
Part Used	Seed
Type Of Preparation	Soxhlet extraction method
Active Constitution	Starch, phenolic compound, Flavonoids, Proteins, minerals, fatty acid
Phytochemical Tests	Positive For Phenols, Flavonoids
Appearance	Brownish-white seeds
Solubility	Partially soluble in water-soluble in ethanol
Odor	Characteristic Odour
Activity	Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, Anti-Inflammatory, Moisturizing.

S. NO.	INGREDIENT NAME	NATURE/USE	FUNCTION	PROPERTY	RANGE
1	Jackfruit seed extract	Active ingredient	Provides antioxidant activity and lip protection	Rich in phenolics, flavonoids, starch	1-5%
2	Bees Wax	Natural wax, Stiffening agent	Provides hardness and structural stability	Yellow waxy solid (insoluble in water)	10-20%
3	Coconut oil	Emollient, Moisturizer	Softens lips and prevents moisture loss	Clear to pale yellow oil	15-30%
4	Shea butter	Emollient, conditioning agent	Improves moisturization and smoothness	Fat-rich semi solid butter	5-15%
5	Vitamin E oil	Antioxidant, Stabilizer	Prevents oxidation and improves stability	Thick yellowish fat-soluble	0.5-2%
6	Vanilla flavor	Flavoring agent	Provides Pleasant aroma and improves sensory acceptability	Characteristic sweet aroma, pale yellow to brown liquid	0.5-2%

AIM

To formulate and evaluate a bioactive lip balm incorporating jackfruit seed and assess its physiochemical properties and stability.

OBJECTIVE

- To extract bioactive constituents from jackfruit seed using a suitable extraction method
- To develop a topical lip balm formulation incorporating jackfruit seed extract.
- To evaluate the physiochemical properties of the formulated lip balm such as Ph, spreadability, melting point and consistency.
- To assess the organoleptic characteristics including appearance, color, odor, and texture.
- To study the stability of the formulation under different storage conditions.
- To evaluate the potential of jack fruit seed extract as a natural bioactive ingredient in cosmetic lip care formulation.

METHOD OF PREPARATION

Extraction process (Soxhlet extraction method)

The jackfruit seeds were cleaned properly, dried, and ground into a coarse powder. Approximately 25 g of the powdered material was transferred into a thimble and subjected to Soxhlet extraction using 95% ethanol as the solvent. The extraction was continued for about 6–8 hours to obtain the phytoconstituents present in the seed sample. After completion, the solvent was removed by gentle heating using a water bath to obtain a concentrated extract. The prepared extract was collected and preserved in a tightly closed container under refrigerated conditions (4°C) for the lip balm formulation.

FORMULATION OF LIIPBALM

S. No	INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY (30g)
1	Jackfruit seed extract	1.5
2	Beeswax	7.5g
3	Shea Butter	10.5g
4	Coconut oil	6g
5	Vitamin E oil	0.75g
6	Vanilla flavour	0.75g

APPARATUS REQUIRED

- Analytical Balance
- Beaker
- water bath
- Thermometer
- Measuring cylinder and pipette
- Lip balm containers
- Glass rod and magnetic stirrer

PREPARATION**Step1: Weighing of Ingredients**

Accurately weigh the required quantities of ingredients using an analytical balance.

Step 2: Melting of base Ingredients

Transfer Beeswax, Shea butter, and Coconut oil into a clean beaker. Heat using a Water bath at 70-75 °C.

Step3: Mixing

Sir the Melted mixture continuously using a glass rod or Magnetic stirrer to obtain a uniform blend.

Step4: Addition of Extract

Add Jack fruit Seed Extract slowly into the melted mixture with continuous stirring.

Step 5: Addition of Additives

Allow slight cooling of the mixture. Then add vitamin E oil and vanilla flavor and mix thoroughly.

STEP 6: Filling

Pour the prepared formulation into lip balm containers or moulds.

STEP 7: Cooling and Solidification Allow the formulation to cool and solidify at room temperature.

STEP 8: Storage

The prepared lip balm is stored in a closed container at 4°C for further evaluation.

EVALUATION TEST**1. Organoleptic Evaluation**

The formulated lip balm was examined for color, odor, appearance, and texture through visual observation.

2. pH Determination

Approximately 1 g of the formulation was dispersed in distilled water, and the pH value was determined using a calibrated pH meter.

3. Spreadability Test

A small quantity of the formulation was placed on a glass slide and evaluated for its spreadability and uniform application characteristics.

4. Melting Point Determination

The melting point of the prepared formulation was determined by gradual heating, and the temperature at which melting occurred was recorded.

5. Homogeneity Test

The formulation was assessed visually for homogeneity, smooth consistency, and absence of coarse particles or lumps.

6. Stability Study

The prepared formulation was stored under refrigerated conditions (4°C) and at room temperature. Physical parameters such as color, odor, texture, and appearance were monitored periodically.

7. Irritation Test

The formulation was tested for potential irritation by topical application and observation for

any signs of redness, itching, or discomfort.

8. Washability Test

The washability of the formulation was evaluated by assessing the ease of removal using water.

MODE OF APPLICATION

1. Clean and dry the lips before application.
2. Take a small quantity of the prepared lip balm using a clean fingertip or apply directly from the container.
3. Apply a thin and uniform layer evenly over the lips
4. Allow the formulation to remain on the lips for proper absorption and moisturizing effect.
5. Reapply as needed to maintain hydration and protection against dryness.

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